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THE IMPACT OF FDI ON INDIAN ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The present research paper is conceptualized and based on collection from various resources like , research paper ,books ,news magazines ,management journals etc. Effective formulation - Effective formulate on of HR strategies is needed for winning the global competition. By implementing sound HR strategies organizations can face the market competition and can achieve all the heights of success.

This paper can inspire managers and experts of their fields for bringing certain changes in their existing HR strategies for better future. By implementing sound HR strategies organizations can become more. The paper includes all the aspects of FDI Pertaining to the investment flow , impact on Indian Economy as well as long-term relationship between GDP and FDI.

Keywords: FDI, GDP, Economy, India

INTRODUCTION

Foreign direct investment is the acquisition of assets in a country by foreign entities for the purpose of control. FDI is ownership of at least 10% of a business. So FDI is the foreign direct investment that a parent company should have to be done in a foreign country and parent company has full control over it.

According to the Ministry of Commerce & Industry, "FDI is freely allowed in all sectors including the services sector, except a few sectors where the existing and notified sectoral policy does not permit FDI beyond a ceiling. FDI for virtually all items/activities can be brought in through the Automatic Route under powers delegated to the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), and for the remaining items/activities through Government approval. Government approvals are accorded on the recommendation of the Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB)."

The historical background of FDI in India can be traced back with the establishment of East India Company of Britain. British capital came to India during the colonial era of Britain in India. However, researchers could not portray the complete history of FDI Pouring in India due to lack of abundant and authentic data. Before independence major Amount of FDI came from the British companies. British companies setup their units in Mining sector and in those sectors that suits their own economic and business interest. After Second World War, Japanese companies entered Indian market and enhanced their Trade with India, yet U.K. remained the most dominant investor in India.

Further, after Independence issues relating to foreign capital, operations of MNCs, gained attention of the policy makers. Keeping in mind the national interests the policy makers designed the FDI policy which aims FDI as a medium for acquiring advanced technology and to mobilize foreign exchange resources. The first Prime Minister of India considered foreign investment as “necessary” not only to supplement domestic capital but also to secure scientific, technical, and industrial knowledge and capital equipments.

Currently FDI has been increasing tremendously increasing due to the positive effect of our Government . FDI in different sectors in 2016 are :-

- Power -49%
- Banking – private :74% and public :26%
- Non-banking financial companies (stock broking, credit cards, financial consulting, etc.) - 100%
- Pension- 49%
- Insurance- 49%
- Multi retail store- 51%
- Telecommunications - 74%
- Private petrol refining - 100%
- Construction development - 100%
- Coal & lignite - 74%
- Trading - 51%
- Electricity - 100%
- Pharmaceuticals - 100%
- Transportation infrastructure - 100 %
- Tourism - 100%
- Mining - 74%
- Advertising - 100%
- Airports – 74%
- Films - 100%

- Domestic airlines - 49%
- Mass transit - 100%
- Pollution control - 100%
- Print media - 26% for newspapers and current events, 100 % for scientific and technical periodicals.

OBJECTIVE:

- TO determine the investment flow of India.
- TO determine the impact of FDI on the Indian economy.
- To Examine the trends and patterns in the FDI across different sectors and from different countries in India
- To build up the hypothesis by the help of focusing on Indian economy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

The empirical work so far has focused on the establishing the relationship between FDI and Economic growth in the home country. These studies take a range or methodological approaches, and find no reciprocal causality relationship between economic growth and FDI. The empirical and theoretical works have tried to establish the connection either between FDI inflows and Economic Growth. We have used Granger Casuality Test.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research designs are concerned with turning the research question into a testing project. The best design depends on your research questions. Every design has its positive and negative sides. The research design has been considered as a "blueprint" for research, dealing with at least four problems: what questions to study, what data are relevant, what data to collect, and how to analyze the results.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY CONTAINS THE FOLLOWING PARAMETERS

Instrument for survey method.: Structured questionnaire

Type of questionnaire: closed ended.

Secondary data: Reference books. Data can be collected by the help review, journals, human resource development plans, magazines, and internet.

Model Specification

The choice of the existing model is based on the fact that it allows for generation and estimation of all the parameters without resulting into unnecessary data mining. The growth model for the study takes the form:

$$GDP=f(FDI) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where GDP and FDI are the gross domestic product and foreign direct investment respectively.

GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST

Pair wise Granger Causality Tests			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Probability
FDI does not Granger Cause GDP	8	12.4342	0.03532
GDP does not Granger Cause FDI		2.21804	0.25625

We reject the null hypothesis that FDI does not cause GDP because F statistic value shows value greater than second hypothesis. Therefore there is evidence that there is a directional movement from FDI to GDP but the probability is low. Similarly there is probability that GDP may be causing FDI because probability for this is comparatively high.

Thus we can say that there is Bi-directional movement between FDI and GDP.

REGRESSION EQUATION: USING ORDINARY LEAST SQUARE

In ordinary least square Method, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the variable and the results of the Ordinary Least Squares Regression are summarized in the Table. The empirical analysis on basis of ordinary Least Square Method suggests that there is positive relationship between foreign direct investment(FDI)investment and GDP and vice versa.

Dependent Variable: GDP				
Method: Least Squares				
Included observations: 10				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1921976.	176246.4	10.90505	0.0000
FDI	35.07503	9.534786	3.678639	0.0062
R-squared	0.628467	Mean dependent var		2423956.
Adjusted R-squared	0.582025	S.D. dependent var		545594.6
S.E. of regression	352732.3	Akaike info criterion		28.56166
Sum squared residue	9.95E+11	Schwarz criterion		28.62218
Log likelihood	-140.8083	F-statistic		13.53238
Durbin-Watson stat	0.959273	Prob(F-statistic)		0.006231

Conclusion of the study of Hypothesis:-

1. In ordinary least square Method, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the variables and the empirical analysis on basis of ordinary Least Square Method suggests that there is positive relationship between foreign direct investment(FDI)investment and GDP and vice versa.
2. In addition, whereas the Ordinary Least squares regression analysis can establish the dependence of either GDP on FDI or vice versa; this does not necessarily imply direction of causation.
3. The Granger causality test finally confirmed the presence of uni-directional causality which runs from economic growth to foreign direct investment.

Analysis and Findings

FACT SHEET ON FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT (FDI)

From APRIL, 2000 to JANUARY, 2015

(Up dated up to January, 2015)

I. CUMULATIVE FDI FLOWS INTO INDIA (2000-2015):

A. TOTAL FDI INFLOWS (from April, 2000 to January, 2015):			
1.	CUMULATIVE AMOUNT OF FDI INFLOWS	-	US\$ 361,320
	(Equity inflows + ‘Re-invested earnings’ + ‘Other capital’)		Million
2.	CUMULATIVE AMOUNT OF FDI EQUITY INFLOWS	Rs. 1,199,386	US\$ 243,107
	(excluding, amount remitted through RBI’s-+NRI Schemes)	crore	Million

B. FDI INFLOWS DURING FINANCIAL YEAR 2014-15 (from April, 2014 to January, 2015):

1.	TOTAL FDI INFLOWS INTO INDIA	-	US\$ 37,758
	(Equity inflows + ‘Re-invested earnings’ + ‘Other capital’)		million
	(as per RBI’s Monthly bulletin dated: 10.03.2015).		
2.	FDI EQUITY INFLOWS	Rs. 155,489	US\$ 25,526
		crore	million

FDI EQUITY INFLOWS (MONTH-WISE) DURING THE FINANCIAL YEAR 2014-15:

Financial Year 2014-15 (April-March)		Amount of FDI Equity inflows	
		(In Rs. Crore)	(In US\$ mn)
1.	April, 2014	10,290	1,705
2.	May, 2014	21,373	3,604
3.	June, 2014	11,508	1,927
4.	July, 2014	21,022	3,500
5.	August, 2014	7,783	1,278

6.	September, 2014	16,297	2,678
7.	October, 2014	16,288	2,655
8.	November, 2014	9,486	1,537
9	December, 2014	13,562	2,161
10	January, 2015	27,880	4,481
2014-15 (from April, 2014 to January, 2015) #		155,489	25,526
2013-14 (from April, 2013 to January, 2014) #		113,401	18,749
% age growth over last year		(+) 37 %	(+) 36 %

D. FDI EQUITY INFLOWS (MONTH-WISE) DURING THE CALENDAR YEAR 2015:

<i>Calendar Year 2015</i> <i>(Jan.-Dec.)</i>		<i>Amount of FDI Equity inflows</i>	
		<i>(In Rs. Crore)</i>	<i>(In US\$ mn)</i>
1.	January, 2015	27,880	4,481
Year 2015 (January, 2015) #		27,880	4,481
Year 2014 (January, 2014) #		13,589	2,189
% age growth over last year		(+) 105 %	(+) 105%

Note: (i) Country & Sector specific analysis is available from the year 2000 onwards, as Company-wise details are provided by RBI from April, 2000 onwards only.

Figures are provisional, subject to reconciliation with RBI, Mumbai.

E: SHARE OF TOP INVESTING COUNTRIES FDI EQUITY INFLOWS

E: SHARE OF TOP INVESTING COUNTRIES FDI EQUITY INFLOWS (Financial years):

Amount Rupees in crores (US\$ in millions)

Ranks	Country	2012-13 (April - March)	2013-14 (April – March)	2014-15 (April '14- January, 2015)	Cumulative Inflows (April '00 - January '15)	%age to total Inflows (in terms of US \$)
1.	MAURITIUS	51,654 (9,497)	29,360 (4,859)	46,663 (7,662)	417,148 (86,187)	36 %
2.	SINGAPORE	12,594 (2,308)	35,625 (5,985)	32,152 (5,262)	157,959 (30,707)	13 %
3.	U.K.	5,797 (1,080)	20,426 (3,215)	6,906 (1,148)	107,791 (21,911)	9 %
4.	JAPAN	12,243 (2,237)	10,550 (1,718)	9,802 (1,611)	90,446 (17,879)	7 %
5.	NETHERLANDS	10,054 (1,856)	13,920 (2,270)	19,094 (3,136)	75,393 (14,371)	6 %
6.	U.S.A.	3,033 (557)	4,807 (806)	9,646 (1,582)	65,376 (13,510)	6 %
7.	CYPRUS	2,658 (490)	3,401 (557)	3,104 (513)	38,834 (7,959)	3 %
8.	GERMANY	4,684 (860)	6,093 (1,038)	5,018 (821)	36,623 (7,340)	3 %
9	FRANCE	3,487 (646)	1,842 (305)	3,617 (592)	22,323 (4,471)	2 %
10.	SWITZERLAND	987	2,084	1,792	14,895	1 %
10.	SWITZERLAND	(180)	(341)	(293)	(3,009)	
TOTAL FDI INFLOWS FROM		121,907	147,518	155,489	1,199,919	
All		(22,423)	(24,299)	(25,525)	(243,228)	

Includes inflows under NRI Schemes of RBI.

Note: (i) Cumulative country-wise FDI equity inflows (from April, 2000 to January,, 2015) are at – Annex-‘A’.

(ii) %age worked out in US\$ terms & FDI inflows received through FIPB/SIA+ RBI’s Automatic Route + acquisition of existing shares only.

Conclusion

A large number of changes that were introduced in the country’s regulatory economic policies heralded the liberalization era of the FDI policy regime in India and brought about a structural breakthrough in the volume of the FDI inflows into the economy maintained a fluctuating and unsteady trend during the study period. It might be of interest to note that more than 50% of the total FDI inflows received by India came from Mauritius, Singapore and the USA.

The main reason for higher levels of investment from Mauritius was that the fact that India entered into a double taxation avoidance agreement (DTAA) with Mauritius were protected from taxation in India.

Therefore, FDI is most hot issue where India is most attractive destination because of its growing market and 65% population are at age 20 -35 .

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